

Oxidation of *tert*-Butylthiocarbamide

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The acid oxidation of thiocarbamides has been known to follow a well-defined pattern^{1,2,3} as shown :

(where R = Phenyl)

Other isomers^{4,5} of III and IV were probable but have not so far been isolated.

The present study on the oxidation of *t*. butylthiocarbamide was undertaken with a view, (i) to see if the special character of the *t*. butyl group influences the reaction in any way, for example, affording products other than III and IV, (ii) to prepare products (I to IV) with a *t*. butyl substituent in place of the phenyl group and (iii) to see if the *t*. butyl group could be used as a blocking group to be subsequently eliminated^{6,7} from the products.

The expected oxidation products (I, II, and III where R=*t*.butyl) were obtained but the final product (IV, R=*t*.C₄H₉) could not be isolated. All the compounds on treatment with hot conc. hydrochloric acid were found to undergo dealkylation and afforded the corresponding unsubstituted products (R=H), found identical with those obtained from the

1. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 154.
2. *Idem, Ibid.*, 1963, 1, 354.
3. *Idem, Ibid.*, 1963, 1, 432.
4. Suresh, *J. Sci. Res. Banaras Hindu Univ.*, 1958-59, LX (2), 94.
5. Joshua, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 391.
6. Nair, Ph. D. Thesis, Banaras Hindu Univ., 1965.
7. Jensen & Holm, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1964, 18, 572.

parent thiocarbamide. For example, the reaction with bis-*t*.butyl formamidine disulphide and sulphide can be shown as follows:

The identity of bis-*t*.butylformamidine sulphide (II, R=*t*.butyl) has been confirmed by its synthesis from *t*.butyl cyanamide and *t*.butyl thiocarbamide in presence of hydrogen chloride. The compound (III) has also been synthesised from *t*.butyl guanidine and *t*.butyl isothiocyanate, thus:

This on dealkylation also furnished the parent amidino thiocarbamide.

Procedure: The required *t*.butyl thiocarbamide was prepared from *t*.butyl isothiocyanate⁸ and ethanolic ammonia^{6,9}.

Bis-t.butylformamidine Disulphide Dihydrobromide. — Finely powdered *t*.butylthiocarbamide (5 gm) was suspended in chloroform (25 ml) and a solution of bromine (about 1.5 ml) in a small quantity of chloroform was added and the reaction mixture allowed to stand for *some*time. The product (6 gm) was washed with chloroform, further purified by precipitation with acetone from its aqueous hydrobromic acid solution, and had m.p. 151°, (Found: C 27.7, H 5.94, N 13.58, S 14.82% : mol. eq. 214.3. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$, 2HBr requires C 28.3, H 5.6, N 13.2, S 15.0% ; mol. eq. 212). It afforded a dipicrate, m.p. 95°. (Found: N 18.85; S 8.46%, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$, $(\text{C}_6\text{S}_2\text{N}_3\text{O}_7)_2$ requires N 19.49, S 8.8%). Like the parent bisformamidine disulphide, its aqueous solutions on standing deposited elementary sulphur, liberated iodine from aqueous potassium iodide and oxidised aqueous hydrogen sulphide to sulphur.

The same product was obtained on oxidation of the *t*.butyl thiocarbamide with bromine in an aq. ethanolic medium, followed by precipitation with acetone, and had m.p. 151°; dipicrate, m.p. 95°. The hydrobromide and the picrate did not depress the m.p.s of the above products.

Bis-t.butylformamidine Sulphide Dihydrochloride. — Bis-*t*.butylformamidine disulphide dihydrobromide (2 gm) was dissolved in methanol (8 ml) and allowed to stand for 24 hr. when elementary sulphur was found to separate. On filtration of sulphur, addition of acetone (10 ml) and passing of hydrogen chloride, a fine crystalline solid was precipitated. It could not be recrystallised from any solvent and further purification was effected by

8. Schmidt, Strickwsky, Seefeldler & Hitzler, *Lichtg. Ann.*, 1950, 368, 192.

9. Kharasch, May & Mayo, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 1580.

reprecipitating it by addition of ether-acetone mixture to its conc. HCl solution. It had m.p. 152°, (Found: C 39.81, H 7.9, N 18.43, S 10.92%; equiv. 150.2; $C_{10}H_{22}N_4S$, 2HCl requires C 39.6, H 7.9, N 18.4, S 10.5%; equiv. 151.5). It afforded a picrate, m.p. 128° (Found: N 20.84, S 4.24%; $C_{10}H_{22}N_4S$, $(C_6H_3N_3O_7)_2$ requires N 20.3, S 4.6%).

Synthesis.—*t*. Butyl thiocarbamide (4 gm) was treated with excess of yellow lead oxide in refluxing acetone. When no further blackening of the lead oxide was noticed, the acetone part was filtered out and a fresh quantity (2 gm) of *t*. butyl thiocarbamide added. HCl was then passed and a small quantity of ether added when a fine colourless crystalline product (3 gm) separated. It was purified by reprecipitation with acetone-ether mixture from its aq. conc. hydrochloric acid solution, and had m.p. 142°. (Found C 39.81, H 8.04%; $C_{10}H_{22}N_4S$, 2HCl requires C 39.6, H 7.9%). It did not show any depression in m.p. when mixed with the above product.

Dealkylation of bis-t-Butylformamidine Disulphide and Monosulphide Salts.—Bis-*t*. butylformamidine disulphide dihydrobromide was boiled with conc. aq. HBr acid. *t*. Butyl bromide was liberated as indicated by the green sooty flame with which the liberated gases burned. On cooling and addition of acetone, a crystalline solid separated, having m.p. 180-182°. This did not show any depression in the m.p. of bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide on mixing.

Similar dealkylation was observed with respect to the bis-*t*. butylformamidine sulphide. The picrate of the product did not depress the m.p. (155°) of bis-formamidine sulphide picrate¹⁰ on mixing. (Found: N 24.85, S 5.9%; $C_8H_8N_4S$, $(C_6H_3N_3O_7)_2$ requires N 24.3, S 5.5%).

t-Butylformamidine-3-*t*-butylthiocarbamide.—Bis-*t*. butylformamidine sulphide dihydrochloride (2 gm) was heated with methanol (15 ml) under reflux for about 15 min. On cooling and concentration no crystalline product could be isolated. The reaction mixture on treatment with alcoholic picric acid, however, deposited a picrate (2.8 gm), m.p. 185° (Found: C 41.92, H 5.07, N 20.91, S 6.55%; $C_{10}H_{22}N_4S$, $C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires C 41.8, H 5.4, N 21.3, S 6.9%).

On debutylation with conc. HCl as in the above experiment, *t*.butyl chloride was formed and from the reaction mixture a picrate, m.p. 206° was obtained. It did not show any depression in mixed m.p. with the picrate of amidinothiocarbamide¹⁰.

The above di-*t*. butylamidinothiocarbamide (picrate m.p. 185°) was found identical with that obtained from *t*-butylisothiocyanate and *t*-butyl-guanidine. Found equiv. 264.2. $C_{10}H_{22}N_4S$, HCl requires equiv. 266.5) m.p. 158°.

Oxidation of the Di-t-butyl thiocarbamide (Picrate).—Bis-*t*. butylformamidine sulphide dihydrochloride (2 gm) was refluxed in methanol (15 ml) for about 15 min. as before and to the resulting solution which has been shown to contain the expected di-*t*. butylamidinothiocarbamide, aq. ethanolic bromine were added. On basification, no base could be isolated but on reacidification and addition of picric acid a picrate (1.5 gm), m.p.

175° was obtained. This was the picrate of di-*t*-butyl guanidine, (Found: N 21.23%; $C_8H_{14}N_3$, $C_8H_{14}N_3O_7$, requires 21.0%). On boiling with conc. HCl acid, *t*-butyl chloride was evolved and another picrate, m.p. 312°, was obtained. It did not show any depression when mixed with the authentic sample of guanidine picrate¹¹.

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